

Infrared Spectra of Gaseous Acetylacetonates of Transition Metals

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The IR spectra of the gaseous acetylacetonates of copper, aluminium, group 3A and some lanthanide metals are investigated in the frequency region 200-3500 cm^{-1} . The analysis of the spectral patterns suggests that copper acetylacetonate (hence written as $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ where AA is the acetylacetonate anion) is a square-planar complex of D_{2h} symmetry and all the remaining $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ chelates ($\text{M}=\text{Al}$, group 3A and lanthanide metals) belong to the D_3 symmetry group. The measurements of the metal-oxygen vibrations provide information on the M-O bond properties and on the stability of these molecules in the gas phase.

THE IR spectra of divalent and trivalent metals acetylacetonates have been the object of several theoretical and spectroscopic studies. Firstly Nakamoto¹ performed a normal-coordinate analysis on the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_2$ ^{1,2} and $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ ³ type complexes assuming a simplified 1:1 model. Subsequently Mikami⁴ carried out a rigorous normal-coordinate treatment on the IR active vibrations of the 1:2 and 1:3 chelates. These calculations provided a more detailed assignment of the IR spectra. The results of ¹³C and ¹⁸O experiments^{5,6} allowed the assignment of the CO and CC stretchings, the nature of which has been a subject of controversy. At last, measurements of the metal isotope shifts on the metal-ligand vibrations⁷ have proved an instrument to characterize the motions involving the metal atom.

However, up to now, the spectroscopic studies carried out on these complexes are available for the solid phase and for liquid solutions and little information was drawn in the low IR region. The aim of this systematic study of the IR spectra of a series of acetylacetonates is to provide a detailed analysis of their spectral features and to achieve their structural and bonding properties in the gas phase. Moreover, the measurements of the metal-oxygen vibrations can be employed to characterize the M-O bond and to foresee the stability of these complexes in the gas phase.

Experimental

The IR spectra were recorded between 200 cm^{-1} and 3500 cm^{-1} by using a Perkin-Elmer IR grating spectrophotometer model 180. The samples were vaporized at ca. 400 K in a pyrex cell, 30 cm path length, heated by a Kanthal wire. The temperature

of the furnace was measured by an iron-constantan thermocouple. The cell was filled with nitrogen at one atm. as a gas diffusion barrier and to avoid the condensation of the vapors on the optical windows. Various scanings were run before and after each experiment in order to distinguish between the background, vapors condensed on the optical windows by chance and the absorptions due to the wished species. Copper and aluminium acetylacetonates were synthesized according to the standard methods⁸; the remaining compounds were highly pure commercial products supplied by the Research Org.-Inorg. Chem. Co. They were purified following the procedure reported in the literature⁸ and outgassed under vacuum for several hours.

Results and Discussion

The IR spectra of the gaseous chelates show a similar spectral pattern consisting of a series of bands which do not suffer the substitution of the metal atom and of some bands which are sensitive to the mass of the metal. The former are therefore related to the vibrations of the acetylacetonate anion and the latter to the motions involving the metal-oxygen bonds. The analysis of these spectra is based on the assumption that the D_{2h} symmetry is held by $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ according to the crystallographic data^{9,10} and that the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ type chelates belong to the D_3 symmetry group by analogy with the structure of $\text{Fe}(\text{AA})_3$ ¹¹. The description of the normal vibrations expected in case of the acetylacetonates of divalent and trivalent metals are summarized in Table 1. The assignment of the bands observed in this study are considerably aided by comparing our measurements with previous investigations on these complexes¹⁻⁶ and taking into account the results of normal-coordinate treatments^{1,3,4}. The conclusions based on ¹⁸O and

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^{13}C isotopic shifts^{5,6} and on the metal isotope effects on the metal-ligand vibrations⁷ have been considered as well.

The bands observed in the IR spectra of gaseous $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$, $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ and $\text{Sc}(\text{AA})_3$ are promptly attributed to the above mentioned species on the basis of recent thermodynamic studies^{1,2,13} which indicate that these species are stable in the gas phase. The comparison among all the spectra suggests that the bands observed in the remaining complexes [except $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$] must belong to the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ gaseous species. Owing to the close similarity of the spectra of the acetylacetonates of the trivalent metals, we restrict the discussion of the spectral features to copper and aluminium acetylacetonates for sake of brevity.

The absorptions ranging between 2850 cm^{-1} and 3060 cm^{-1} are confidently attributed to the CH_3 and CH stretchings and further discussions are needless; likewise, the bands around 1410 cm^{-1} and 1390 cm^{-1} belong to the CH_3 deformations. A number of bands is present in all the spectra between 1530 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} where the CO and CC stretching vibrations are expected. Nakamoto⁷ based the assignment of these bands on the ground of normal-coordinate calculations; these modes were found slightly coupled with each other⁴, however, ^{13}C and ^{18}O isotopic substitution^{5,6} indicates that the CO stretching occurs at a higher frequency than the CC vibration. The IR spectra of solid acetylacetonates²⁻⁴ show a band around 1550 cm^{-1} which Mikami⁴ assigned to a combination mode while Pinchas⁶ assigned it to the symmetric CO stretching. According to the results of the vibrational analysis reported in Table 1, two IR active vibrations are

since the spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ shows peaks at 1583 cm^{-1} and 1560 cm^{-1} which we assign to the CO stretchings of B_{2u} and B_{1u} symmetry species respectively while the CC stretching of B_{2u} symmetry should correspond to the band at 1527 cm^{-1} . As regards the assignment of these vibrations for the 1 : 3 complexes, the spectrum of $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$, for instance, reveals absorptions at 1580 , 1570 , and 1560 cm^{-1} assigned to the CO stretchings while the bands at 1543 and 1532 cm^{-1} to the CC stretchings of E symmetry. The remaining CC stretching of B_{1u} species is identified in the band at 1281 cm^{-1} in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ and that of E type at 1288 cm^{-1} for $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$. The assignment of these latter bands is based on the conclusions carried out by several authors^{1,4} and confirmed by ^{18}O isotopic shift measurements⁶ which also suggest the coupling of this vibration with the CR stretching ($\text{R}-\text{CH}_3$). The band falling around 1190 cm^{-1} in all the spectra is assigned to the CH in-plane deformation as supported by deuteration⁴. The respective out-of-plane deformation corresponds to the absorption at 786 cm^{-1} (B_{3u}) which appears in the spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ and at 803 cm^{-1} (E) and 783 cm^{-1} (A_2) in the spectrum of $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$. Particularly interesting is the assignment of the CR stretchings. The vibrational analysis foresees two IR active modes (B_{1u} and B_{2u}) in the square-planar complex and three IR frequencies (A_2 and 2E) for the 1 : 3 chelates. Normal-coordinate treatments¹⁻⁴ provide the position of the corresponding frequencies, however, both the spectra of the divalent^{1,2,4} and trivalent^{3,4} metals acetylacetonates recorded in the solid phase show only one band lying between $930-940\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These motions should be coupled with the CO stretching as suggested by ^{18}O and ^{13}C experiments^{5,6}.

Particular emphasis is reserved to the absorptions below 700 cm^{-1} where the ring deformations and the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ vibrations fall. Several modes lying here are coupled with each other^{4,7}. The absorptions around 690 cm^{-1} and 660 cm^{-1} attributed to a planar ring deformation and to the CR bending respectively, both coupled with the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching as confirmed by metal isotope shifts measurements⁷. The out-of-plane ring deformation is assigned to the bands observed at 614 cm^{-1} and at 584 cm^{-1} in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ and $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ respectively; this vibration should contain a small amount of $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching character^{2-4,8}. In case of $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ two IR active $\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ stretchings of B_{1u} and B_{2u} symmetry are foreseen (see Table 1). The B_{1u} vibration is identified in the absorption at 468 cm^{-1} which should be coupled with the CR stretching according to the conclusions of Mikami⁴ and Nakamoto⁷. The remaining $\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ stretching of B_{2u} species should fall around 300 cm^{-1} ^{4,6} and it can be reliably recognized in the band at 293 cm^{-1} . As concerns the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching modes occurring in the 1 : 3 chelates, three of them are IR active under the D_3 symmetry (A_2 and 2E). According to the normal-coordinate calculations^{3,4}, the peak

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF THE NORMAL VIBRATIONS OCCURRING IN THE 1 : 2 AND 1 : 3 CHELATES

$\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$, D_{2h} symmetry	
$\text{Cu}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{C}$ and $\text{C}-\text{R}^{(a)}$ stretchings	A_g , B_{2g} , B_{1u} , B_{2u}
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretchings	A_g , B_{1u}
Ring in-plane deformations	2A_g , 2B_{2g} , 2B_{1u} , 2B_{2u}
$\text{C}-\text{R}^{(a)}$ in-plane deformations	A_g , B_{1g} , B_{1u} , B_{2u}
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ in-plane deformations	E_g , B_{2u}
Ring out-of-plane deformations	3B_{2g} , 3B_{2u} , 2A_u
$\text{C}-\text{R}^{(a)}$ out-of-plane deformations	2B_{1g} , A_u , B_{2u}
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ out-of-plane deformations	B_{2g} , B_{2u}
$\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ type chelates, D_3 symmetry	
$\text{M}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{C}$ and $\text{C}-\text{R}^{(a)}$ stretchings	A_1 , A_2 , 2E
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretchings	A_1 , E
Ring in-plane deformations	2A_1 , 5A_2 , 6E
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ in-plane deformations	A_1 , E
Ring out-of-plane deformations	3A_1 , 2A_2 , 6E
$\text{C}-\text{H}$ out-of-plane deformations	A_2 , E
^(a) $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$	

expected both for the CO and CC stretchings under the D_{2h} symmetry and three IR active modes are foreseen for the same vibrations in case of the 1 : 3 chelates. These expectations are completely fulfilled

which we observe at 495 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ corresponds to one of the degenerate $\text{Al}-\text{O}$ stretchings; the A_2 and the other E vibrations are identified in the absorptions at 370 and 238 cm^{-1} respectively.

One of the most remarkable differences among the spectra of the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ complexes is the presence of a strong absorption around 535 cm^{-1} which only appears in the spectra of the former chelates. This band corresponds to the frequency at 515 cm^{-1} of the enol form of acetylacetonone^{1,4} and according to the previous investigations it is assigned to a ring planar deformation, coupled with the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching^{6,15}. A series of absorptions are detected in the spectra of copper and of the remaining acetylacetonates in the far IR region. The bands at 293 , 268 and 219 cm^{-1} most probably are related to the bands at 291 , 268 and 217 cm^{-1} observed in the spectrum of solid $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$. In this region we observe a further line at 210 cm^{-1} ; this band, never observed up to now, could correspond to that calculated by Mikami⁴ at 207 cm^{-1} and which we assign to a in-plane ring deformation. As regards the investigation of this range in the case of the trivalent metals acetylacetonates, the only available assignment reported in the literature is that proposed by Mikami⁴ for $\text{Fe}(\text{AA})_3$. The IR spectra of solid $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ ^{1,5}, $\text{La}(\text{AA})_3$ ^{1,5} and $\text{Nd}(\text{AA})_3$ ^{1,5} do not show the presence of absorptions below 370 cm^{-1} . Our gas phase spectra, however, display peaks at 270 , 238 , 215 and 207 cm^{-1} which have been assigned according to the normal-coordinate analysis of Nakamoto³ and Mikami⁴. It must be pointed out that some vibrations as the CR in-plane deformations and few other ring deformations occurring in the 1 : 3 chelates are expected at frequencies very close to each other¹⁻⁴ so that the broadness of the corresponding absorptions does not allow to reveal such bands.

Conclusions :

The analysis of the IR spectra of the gaseous acetylacetonates of copper and of the trivalent transition metals indicates that some differences mark the spectra of the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ chelates from the $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ complex as a different number of absorptions related to the CO, CC and CR stretchings and for the presence of a characteristic band ranging around 30 cm^{-1} in the 1 : 3 chelates. The spectroscopical expectations for the 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes are in each case completely fulfilled.

The measurements of the shift of the band at 515 cm^{-1} of the enol form of acetylacetonone^{1,4} upon complexing and of the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching frequency (T-that at the highest wavenumber) were taken into account by some investigators^{1,15} to characterize the nature of the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond and to foresee the stability of these complexes. It seems therefore natural to us to extend this study to the gaseous

acetylacetonates on the basis of our measurements carried out in the gas phase. Measurements of the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ vibrations are particularly suitable to achieve directly this kind of information as the strength of the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond and the stability of the chelate. The $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching frequencies occur at 495 cm^{-1} and at 468 cm^{-1} in the gaseous acetylacetonates of aluminium and copper, the corresponding frequencies measured for the solid phase are 490 and 455 cm^{-1} respectively. Nakamoto³ concluded by comparing the calculated force constants that the $\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ bond has a partial double bond character and that the $\text{Al}-\text{O}$ bond is strongly covalent. The present results suggest that the same conclusions can be drawn for the gaseous $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{AA})_2$ complexes as well. In order to put forward conclusions on the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond character for the remaining complexes, the values of the highest $\text{M}-\text{O}$ frequencies were plotted versus LogM (M =mass of the metal atom in a.m.u.). These frequencies follow a linear trend and the corresponding $\nu\text{Al}-\text{O}$ was found to be aligned with them (see Fig. 1). The trend observed most probably reflects the change in mass of the metal suggesting therefore that the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ force

Fig. 1. Plot of the experimental $\text{M}-\text{O}$ frequencies (cm^{-1}) versus LogM for the $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ type chelates; (the LogM scale above 2.0 is different from that below 2.0): a=Al, b=Sc, c=Y, d=La, e=Nd, f=Sm, g=Eu, h=Dy, i=Ho, l=Yb and m=Lu.

constants are approximately the same for all the 1 : 3 chelates and quite close to that of the $\text{Al}-\text{O}$ bond³. This behavior should indicate that the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond character in Sc, Y, La and in the lanthanides is as covalent as that of the $\text{Al}-\text{O}$ bond. On this ground, we have derived two sets of linear equations, one including the $\nu\text{Al}-\text{O}$, $\nu\text{Sc}-\text{O}$, $\nu\text{Y}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{La}-\text{O}$ frequencies and another including the remaining $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ frequencies (M =Nd, Sm, Eu, Dy, Ho, Yb and Lu) which correlate the highest $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ values to LogM . The least-squares treatment yields for the former set the following straight line: $\bar{\nu}(\text{cm}^{-1}) = 586 - 64 \text{ LogM}$ and for the latter one the equation: $\bar{\nu}(\text{cm}^{-1}) = 584 - 63 \text{ LogM}$. Our conclusions seem to be strengthened by the insignificant shifts measured for the band at 515 cm^{-1} of the enol form of acetylacetonone^{1,4} which ranges from 535 cm^{-1} to

531 cm^{-1} passing from $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3$ to $\text{Lu}(\text{AA})_3$. On this basis we foresee the same stability of gaseous $\text{Al}(\text{AA})_3^{1,2}$ for the gaseous $\text{M}(\text{AA})_3$ type chelates.

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